

D6.1 Quality Assurance Plan

Prepared by: UOULU

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

AGA	Annotated Grant Agreement
CA	Consortium Agreement
CFS	Certificate on the Finance Statement
DoA	Description of the Action
EB	Executive Board
EC	European Commission
ECAS	European Commission Authentication Service
EU	The European Union
EU GA	EU Grant Agreement project specific
FA	Funding Authority
GA	General Assembly
PO	Project Officer from the European Commission
PM	Project Manager
PSC	Project Scientific Coordinator
QAP	Quality Assurance Plan
TL(s)	Task Leader(s)
WP	Work Package
WPL(s)	Work Package Leader(s)

1 Introduction

1.1 About the Quality Assurance Plan (QAP)

Quality Assurance Plan has been designed to serve as a quick guide/handbook for the day-to-day operation during the project. It serves as a reference book for all project members to identify their roles and responsibilities and to address project-related processes. It standardises various elements of the project e.g. project reports, Deliverables, etc. through the use of agreed procedures and templates where relevant.

This QAP will be a dynamic document and will be updated as required throughout the project. The latest version of the manual will always be available at the project shared workspace.

1.2 Document overview

This document is structured as follows:

- Section 2: provides general information about the project.
- Section 3: provides an overview about the legal aspects of the project.
- Section 4: describes an organisational structure of the project and roles in the project.
- Section 5: delineates the different ways of communication within the project.
- Section 6: describes reporting-related processes within the project. This includes project-internal reporting but also external reporting to European Commission.
- Section 7: provides an overview about the payment.
- Section 8: provides an overview about Deliverables.
- Section 9: states the rules for dissemination within the project.

1.3 Precedence

The general principles for the project execution are defined in the EU Grant Agreement (EU GA), the Description of the action (DoA) and the Consortium Agreement (CA). This Project book does not replace any of these agreements, nor does it replace any of the EU guidelines for project implementation and documentation.

Where there are any inconsistencies between these documents, the following order of precedence should be applied:

- 1) EU Grant Agreement (EU GA) including Description of the action
- 2) Consortium Agreement (CA)
- 3) Quality Assurance Plan (present document)

2 General Project Information

2.1 Project Summary

The ICEBERG project has a two-fold aim: 1) to comprehensively assess sources, types, distributions and impacts of pollution in combination with chronic climate-induced stressors on ecosystems and communities in the European Arctic's land-ocean continuum using a One Health approach, and 2) to develop strategies for enhancing community-led resilience strategies, as well as pollution-control governance approaches. To this end, the project focusses on three (sub)regional case studies: western Svalbard, southern Greenland and northern Iceland.

ICEBERG will investigate known and emerging pollutants, including macro-, micro, nanoplastics, ship emissions, wastewater, persistent organic pollutants (POPs) and terrigenous elements (heavy metals). To assess the effects of pollutant discharges from Arctic ship traffic, freshwater discharge/cryosphere meltwater, wastewater and land-based atmospheric pollution on the marine food web, the project will use model simulations, remote sensing, in-situ observations and measurements. ICEBERG will analyse the sanitary quality of the food chain by characterising chemical contaminants using an exposomic approach, gaining a comprehensive understanding of the synergistic impacts of climate change and pollution on human health. It will evaluate the toxicological impact of micro- and nano-plastics and POPs on human digestive health. The project will develop automatic marine litter detection tools combining the use of drones, artificial intelligence (AI) and citizen science. ICEBERG will incorporate multi-stakeholder and gender-based approaches to assess the impacts, risks and vulnerabilities on Indigenous and local communities and co-create scenarios of change. Scenario modelling will be used to co-design local pollution-control strategies, which includes both mitigation (reducing pollution) and adaptation (reducing vulnerability to pollution). Finally, ICEBERG will create novel governance approaches for pollution-control in the Arctic at multiple scales.

Table 1. Project partners

No.	Partner	Short Name	Country
1	OULUN YLIOPISTO	UOULU	Finland
2	ASSOCIACAO PARA O DESENVOLVIMENTO DO (ATLANTIC INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH CENTRE)	AIRCentre	Portugal
3	BARCELONA SUPERCOMPUTING CENTER CENTRO NACIONAL DE SUPERCOMPUTACION	BSC	Spain
4	FUNDACJA FORSCIENCE	forScience	Poland
5	HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM FUR OZEANFORSCHUNG KIEL	GEOMAR	Germany
6	HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM POTSDAM DEUTSCHES GEOFORSCHUNGSZENTRUM	GFZ	Germany
7	HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM FUR UMWELTFORSCHUNG GMBH	UFZ	Germany
8	INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE POUR L'AGRICULTURE, L'ALIMENTATION ET L'ENVIRONNEMENT	INRAE	France
9	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	ISP-CNR	Italy

No.	Partner	Short Name	Country
10	KASKAS MEDIA OY	KASKAS	Finland
11	CHRISTIAN-ALBRECHTS-UNIVERSITAET ZU KIEL	CAU	Germany
12	LAPIN YLIOPISTO	ULAP	Finland
13	ECOLE NATIONALE VETERINAIRE, AGROALIMENTAIRE ET DE L'ALIMENTATION NANTES ATLANTIQUE	ONIRIS	France
14	SCIDRONES TEXNOVLASTOS IKE	SCI	Greece
15	STOFNUN VILHJALMS STEFANSSONAR	SAI	Iceland
16	WOMEN OF THE ARCTIC	WoA	Finland

3 Legal Aspects

3.1 Grant Agreement (EU GA)

The EU GA forms the legal basis for the implementation of the project. It consists of:

- Terms and Conditions (this is the core contract);
- Annex 1 Description of the action (DoA);
- Annex 2 Estimated budget for the action;
- Annex 2a Additional information on unit costs and contributions;
- Annex 3 Accession forms;
- Annex 4 Model for the financial statements;
- Annex 5 Specific rules.

Although the core contract is signed between the EU and the Coordinator of the project, all partners have become individual contract partners with the commission by signing the accession forms.

The EU GA must be kept by all partners and should be provided to the auditor in case of an audit. It is downloadable on the participant portal in the document library of the project and on the shared workspace [here](#).

3.2 Consortium Agreement (CA)

Whereas the EU GA is signed between the EU and the partners, the CA is signed between the partners themselves. It arranges in more detail the provisions of the EU GA, such as but not limited to: financial issues, payments, management, decision making, conflict resolution, intellectual property rights and liability.

The CA must also be kept by the partners and must be shown in the case of audits. It is downloadable on the shared workspace [here](#).

3.3 Amendments

During the project, circumstances may arise to call for a request to the EU for an amendment of the EU GA. Reasons may vary, but could be:

- change of partner(s);
- change of legal entity;
- changes in the Budget (EU GA: Annex 2);
- changes in the DoA (EU GA: Annex 1).

In case an amendment is needed, the Project Coordinator shall submit such a request after an autonomous decision by all partners in the General Assembly. After approval, the Project Coordinator shall distribute the revised EU GA to the partners, replacing the former versions.

Budget changes that do not affect the content of DoA can be taken care of by the consortium itself via a decision in the General Assembly and informing the Project Officer. Amendments may be requested by any of the project partners.

4 Roles

4.1 Organisational structure

Figure 1 below describes the organisational structure within the project.

Figure 1. Project organisational structure

4.2 Project Coordinator

The Project Coordinator (PC) is the University of Oulu (UOULU) and is responsible for efficient project management and activities with respect to time, budget and quality.

The project coordination is performed by:

- the Project Scientific Coordinator (PSC), Prof. Thora Herrmann (UOULU), who is responsible for the scientific development of the project. The main responsibility is to ensure that the main goals of the project are pursued. The PSC cooperates closely with Work Package Leaders to guarantee that the project delivers the expected impact.
- the Project Manager (PM), Dr. Docent Élise Lépy (UOULU), is responsible for the administrative, legal and financial management of the project as well as for organisational matters.

The PC will be the intermediary between the project consortium and the Funding Authority (FA) and shall perform all tasks assigned to it as described in the EU GA to be concluded with the Funding Authority. The everyday management of the research and development activities is explicitly delegated to the WP Leaders.

The PC responsibilities include:

- monitoring compliance by the Parties with their obligations and ensuring that all partners are working for the same goal;
- all contractual obligations required by the FA. Providing overviews of the work progress to the FA; collecting and reviewing financial, technical and administrative reports to verify consistency with the project tasks before transmitting them to the FA and submitting progress and final reports, financial statements and other Deliverables;
- administering the community contribution regarding its allocation between beneficiaries and activities, in accordance with the EU GA and the decisions taken by the consortium. The PC will ensure that all the appropriate payments are made to the other beneficiaries without unjustified delay. The PC will take care of financial account management, advance payments, withholding payments and assistance to partners for Cost Statements preparation;
- informing the FA of the distribution of the community financial contribution and the date of transfers to the beneficiaries, when required by the EU GA or the FA;
- maintaining contact with the FA (Project Officer) and notifying the Project Officer about developments that would alter the EU GA;
- preparing a progress report every 6 months for the Project Officer. The report describes the main achievements of each WP/Task, the feedback of the Advisory Board meetings (if they took place), the challenges and the participation/organisation of events;
- coordinating and supervising all legal and contractual aspects, knowledge management and exploitation activities;
- maintaining the communication among the partners of the project and facilitating the communication between the consortium and the FA (contact to be made with the partners once a month);
- administrative management: preparation and maintenance of project calendar, monitoring budget, Deliverables and Milestones, guaranteeing the achievement of the objectives and the accomplishment of the proposed plan in dates and budget, preparation of meetings and related documentation and execution of the meetings decisions, set-up and maintenance of project documentation archive;
- in terms of decision-making mechanism on operational issues, the PC calls the General Assembly to emergency meetings if needed.

The PC's operational coordination tasks to be performed in cooperation with the Project Management Group are:

- guidance and support of WP Leaders to ensure quality results and timely reporting;
- technical coordination and integration between Work Packages;
- supervision of the implementation;
- organisation and chairing of the General Assembly and Project Management Group meetings;
- monitoring IPR issues.

4.3 General Assembly (GA)

The General Assembly (GA) is responsible for the decision-making of the project and consists of one representative from each partner in the consortium. It is chaired by the project coordination team.

The GA shall be free to act on its own initiative to formulate proposals and take decisions. In addition, all proposals made by the Project Management Group shall also be considered and decided upon by the GA.

Table 2. General Assembly Members

Partners' No.	Partner	Representative	Email	Country
1	UOULU	Thora Herrmann <i>Élise Lépy (substitute)</i>	thora.herrmann@oulu.fi <i>elise.lepy@oulu.fi</i>	Finland
2	AIRCentre	Jose Luiz Moutinho	jose.moutinho@aircentre.org	Portugal
3	BSC	Marta Terrado	marta.terrado@bsc.es	Spain
4	forScience	Barbara Jóźwiak	biuro@forscience.pl	Poland
5	GEOMAR	Christa Marandino	cmarandino@geomar.de	Germany
6	GFZ	Anne S. Chahine	anne.chahine@rifs-potsdam.de	Germany
7	UFZ	Christine Liang <i>Peter Dietrich (substitute)</i>	christine.liang@ufz.de <i>peter.dietrich@ufz.de</i>	Germany
8	INRAE	Muriel Mercier-Bonin	muriel.mercier-bonin@inrae.fr	France
9	ISP-CNR	Tommaso Tesi	tommaso.tesi@cnr.it	Italy
10	KASKAS	Paavo Antikainen	paavo.antikainen@kaskas.fi	Finland
11	CAU	Annegret Kuhn	akuhn@politik.uni-kiel.de	Germany
12	ULAP	Timo Koivurova <i>Adam Stepien (substitute)</i>	timo.koivurova@ulapland.fi <i>adam.stepien@ulapland.fi</i>	Finland
13	ONIRIS	Gaud Dervilly	gaud.dervilly@inrae.fr	France
14	SCI	Apostolos Papakonstantinou	apapak@scidrones.com	Greece
15	SAI	Joan Nymand Larsen	jnl@unak.is	Iceland
16	WoA	Tahnee Prior	tahnee.prior@gmail.com	Finland

Responsibilities: The GA will be the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium. The PC handles all documentation of the GA and prepares the issues to be handled by the assembly. The GA responsibilities include:

- to ensure that the project is executed in line with the needs and requirements of the participants;
- to make major strategic decisions: to solve conflicts, to tackle technical risks and to manage changes of the work plan;
- to monitor the overall quality of the project;
- to handle changes to the plan (including Budget) and redistribution of finances, based on the PMG suggestions;
- to propose changes to Annex 1 "Description of the action" and Annex 2 "Estimated budget for the action" of EC-Grant Agreement (EU GA) to be agreed by the Funding Authority;
- to accept the plans for dissemination and exploitation of the results;
- to handle all project agreements and IPR issues according to the Consortium Agreement;

- evolution of the consortium.

The General Assembly meets at least once every six months. The ordinary GA meetings will be organised face-to-face once a year as part of the annual consortium meetings, and as online meetings in between.

Meeting practices: The material for the GA meetings, prepared by the PC as the secretary, will be sent 14 days before the meeting. The PC will prepare the minutes of the meeting (MoM) and send a draft to the GA members within 10 days after the meeting. The PC will be in charge of distributing the documents and information on decisions taken to all relevant parties.

Decision-making: Each partner shall have the right to nominate a representative to participate in the GA meetings. Each GA member shall have one vote. The GA decisions are valid if 2/3 of the voting members are present or represented. A decision takes 2/3 majority of the votes. A member can exercise a veto on a decision or a part of a decision if the legitimate interests of the member are severely affected. Further rules are defined in section 6 of the CA.

4.4 Project Management Group (PMG)

The Project Management Group (PMG) is the supervisory body for the execution of the project and is responsible for the implementation of the decisions of the GA. The responsibilities of the PMG are:

- to review the progress of the work and to decide on the next steps to be taken in order to achieve the aims of the project;
- to coordinate the Work Packages, monitor the project implementation and decide about the publication of project information materials and practical issues regarding the implementation;
- to support the PC to ensure that the technical objectives and activities of the project are of high quality and met on schedule;
- to oversee the absolute technical matters pertaining to the work plan (early identification of any risks or problems in the project) and maintain and update the risk management plan;
- to prepare and propose decisions to be made by the General Assembly and prepare the GA materials, meetings and agenda;
- to execute and implement the GA decisions.

The PMG consists of the Work Package Leaders. The PMG members will report monthly on their respective WPs during the monthly consortium meetings. The PMG will also communicate about the project's progress to the Advisory Board every 6 months. In addition, online PMG meetings will be arranged as much as needed. The leader of WP6 (Management) shall chair all meetings of the PMG, unless decided otherwise by a majority of two-thirds.

Table 3. Project Management Group Members

WP No.	WP Title	Partner	Name	Email
WP1	Assessment of pollutions sources, distribution, and impacts in Arctic ecosystems	forScience GEOMAR	Barbara Józwiak Christa Marandino	biuro@forscience.pl cmarandino@geomar.de
WP2	Risk assessment and local resilience strategies for ecosystems and communities	UOULU SAI	Thora Herrmann Joan Nymand Larsen	thora.herrmann@oulu.fi jnl@unak.is

WP No.	WP Title	Partner	Name	Email
WP3	Facilitating effective science-based pollution-control governance	ULAP CAU	Adam Stepien Annegret Kuhn	adam.stepien@ulapland.fi akuhn@politik.uni-kiel.de
WP4	Co-Creation, Ethics, Diversity, Equity and Inclusion	WoA	Tahnee Prior	tahnee.prior@gmail.com
WP5	Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Outreach	KASKAS	Paavo Antikainen	paavo.antikainen@kaskas.fi
WP6	Project Coordination and Management	UOULU	Élise Lépy	elise.lepy@oulu.fi

4.5 Work Package and Task Leaders (WPLs and TLs)

The Work Package Leaders (WPLs) and the Task Leaders (TLs) are responsible for the detailed implementation of the WPs and Tasks as well as preparation of the corresponding Deliverables and Milestones.

The WPLs are responsible for the following activities:

- reporting progress at PMG and monthly consortium meetings;
- immediately reporting major decisions related to any deviation to the work plan;
- coordinating the activities of the TLs;
- highlighting any partners whose contributions are of insufficient or of unacceptable quality.

The WPLs ensure that the PC is informed about WP developments. Adjustment to work must be agreed by the PC.

In the WPs, each Partner is responsible for allocating sufficient manpower, financial and other resources in order to carry out the tasks assigned to him/her and for delivering cost statements and providing information and data (financial and other) to the PC to ensure that documents can be elaborated and submitted on time.

4.6 Advisory Board (AB)

The project includes an Advisory Board (AB) who has a supporting role in the project. Specifically, the AB will advise from the perspective of the professional sector of the ICEBERG project.

The AB will be involved in the following actions:

- provide advice and feedback for Work Package progress, field work and report Deliverables;
- attend 6 meetings during the life of the project (Months 6, 13, 18, 25, 30 and 35);
- give feedback on the mid-term and final report to the EC (Months 18 and 30);
- take part in the policy feedback sessions;
- participate at the final conference in Brussels disseminating key project outcomes;
- be the liaison for fieldwork, for example, support organising workshops with community members, reaching out to local people, schools etc. for interviews and help planning the community consultation meetings.

Table 4. Advisory Board Members

Name / Organisation	Foreseen role (e.g. pilot, user board, etc.)	Country	Email
Huld Hafliðadóttir/ STEM Husavik / HUsavik Knowledge Centre	Liaison for fieldwork in Husavik	Iceland	Huld@hac.is
Erik Kielsen	Liaison for fieldwork in Greenland, i.e. Qaqortoq, Narsaq, Nanortalik Translator: Kalaallisut – English, English - Kalaallisut	Greenland	Erikkielsen@icloud.com

4.7 Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach board (DECO)

The DECO Board's key objective is to design, tailor, localize, test and execute DECO activities related to the project. The DECO Board consists of one representative per work package, one representative per case study and the Scientific Coordinator. The Board meets regularly to ensure smooth communication within the project.

Table 5. DECO Board Members

WP/Case Study	Names of Representatives/Affiliation	Email
WP1	Markus Schartau / GEOMAR	mschartau@geomar.de
WP2	Apostolos Papakonstantinou / SCI Gaud Dervilly / ONIRIS (Substitute)	apapak@scidrones.com gaud.dervilly@inrae.fr
WP3	Adam Stepien / ULAP José Luiz Moutinho / AIRCentre (Substitute) Valerie de Liedekerke / AIRCentre (Substitute)	adam.stepien@ulapland.fi jose.moutinho@aircentre.org valerie.deliedekerke@aircentre.org
WP4	Anne Chahine / GFZ (RIFS) Christine Liang / UFZ (Substitute)	anne.chahine@rifs-potsdam.de christine.liang@ufz.de
WP5	Paavo Antikainen / KASKAS KASKAS Team (Substitute)	paavo.antikainen@kaskas.fi iceberg-wp5@lists oulu.fi
WP6	Élise Lépy / UOULU	elise.lepy@oulu.fi
Svalbard	Beatrice Rosso / CNR	beatrice.rosso@isp.cnr.it
Greenland (Kalaallit Nunaat)	Ilona Mettiäinen / ULAP	ilona.mettiainen@ulapland.fi
Iceland	Joan Nymand Larsen / SAI	jnl@unak.is
Scientific Coordinator	Thora Herrmann / UOULU	thora.herrmann@oulu.fi

4.8 Meetings

Monthly consortium meetings are held every last Friday of each month. All project members are invited to participate and hear the progress of the project given by WPLs. The minutes of the meetings are taken by

the PC and are submitted to the consortium within 10 days.

At online meetings, it might be useful to record the meeting to fix the minutes. However, the meeting should only be recorded after announcement at the start of the meeting and only if there are no objections. Recordings will be deleted once the minutes are published on the shared workspace.

Annual consortium meetings are plenary meetings and parallel sessions combining technical progress. They will be held once a year and will gather the entire consortium as well as the AB. They will take place in Iceland, Italy and Belgium. The minutes of the meetings will be taken by the PC.

Costs for travel and accommodation to participate in these meetings have to be covered by each partner's own budget. Costs related to the organisation of the three annual consortium meetings should be borne by the PC.

Other meetings may be organised by two or more partners to discuss technical aspects of the project. For every meeting taken place, **minutes** should be sent to the PC and partners involved within 10 days after the meeting.

Table 6. Planned project meetings

Project meeting	Month/Year	Location
Kick-Off Meeting	24 th -25 th January 2024	Oulu, Finland
M6 PMG + AB	June 2024	Online
M6 GA	June 2024	Online
M13 Annual consortium meeting + AB	January 2025 (tbc)	Akureyri, Iceland
M18 PMG + AB	June 2025	Online
M18 GA	June 2025	Online
M25 Annual consortium meeting + AB	January 2026 (tbc)	Bologna, Italy
M30 PMG + AB	June 2026	Online
M30 GA	June 2026	Online
M35 Annual consortium meeting + AB	November 2026	Brussels, Belgium

5 Communication

5.1 Internal communication

Internal communication is considered the communication within the consortium.

5.1.1 E-mail

As a general rule, the subject of all emails exchanged in the project should begin with "ICEBERG" in order to enable the efficient use of filters in emails!

Many people may be working on several different projects and are likely to receive numerous emails every day, therefore, a standard subject title is proposed. This helps to quickly recognize the project related emails.

Project related e-mails should include in the subject title the '**Project name**' and **WP number (if applicable)** followed by a more specific description of the subject, deadline for feedback or reply, see below an example:

[Subject: ICEBERG / Kick-off meeting minutes – Deadline feedback 5 February 2024]

Furthermore, it is required to copy the scientific coordinator (thora.herrmann@oulu.fi) and the project manager (elise.lepy@oulu.fi) in all WP6 and other project coordination related e-mail communication.

Twelve general mailing lists have been created:

General Assembly:	iceberg-ga@lists.oulu.fi
Project Management Group:	iceberg-pmg@lists.oulu.fi
Advisory Board:	iceberg-ab@lists.oulu.fi
DECO Board:	iceberg-deco@lists.oulu.fi
Entire project_members	iceberg-members@lists.oulu.fi
Entire project_admin	iceberg-admin@lists.oulu.fi
WP1	iceberg-wp1@lists.oulu.fi
WP2	iceberg-wp2@lists.oulu.fi
WP3	iceberg-wp3@lists.oulu.fi
WP4	iceberg-wp4@lists.oulu.fi
WP5	iceberg-wp5@lists.oulu.fi
WP6	iceberg-wp6@lists.oulu.fi

5.1.2 Internal Communication Platform

Shared workspace

A project shared workspace was set up to act as repository of any project documents. The shared workspace should be used to store all project management information, such as reports, Deliverables and any working documents etc. The address of the ICEBERG shared workspace is: [ICEBERG | General | Microsoft Teams](#)

Every member of the consortium has been invited to join the project workspace. In case of problems/need for a new account, please contact iceberg-wp6@lists.oulu.fi.

Please note that all files are accessible to everyone who has been added to TEAMS so don't use the TEAMS to store sensitive, proprietary information. Large data files (such as simulation results, etc.) should be stored by partners themselves.

Mailing and contact list

The project will keep an email and contact list held in an Excel spreadsheet. The contact list can be accessed [here](#).

Within this list, all project members are included. Additional information, like partner organisation, roles in the project and participation in a specific WP, is included.

When starting a new email, you should always use the latest version available at the Workspace. DO NOT create your own local copies of this list; it is most likely outdated if you are going to use it again. If you want to change some data in the mailing and contact list, please contact iceberg-wp6@lists oulu.fi.

Rules for using email

Please follow the following rules for using the mailing list. DO NOT send emails with attachments. Instead, upload the file on TEAMS and include the correct link within your mail. Before sending an email, consider carefully who you are targeting, and check the distribution list names.

5.2 Communication with the Project Officer

The Project Coordinator is responsible for the communication with the Horizon Europe Project Officer. Hence, the PC is the only contact point between the ICEBERG project partners and the European Commission representatives regarding the project.

5.3 External communication

External communication is considered towards parties outside the consortium, target groups of the project, other stakeholders, rights holders and the EU Project Officer.

External communication is part of WP5 Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Outreach for which the partner, KASKAS, is responsible (Paavo Antikainen paavo.antikainen@kaskas.fi).

Communication of project results is an important part of a Horizon Europe project. You will find more information in the deliverable 'D5.2: DECO strategy'.

5.3.1 Project website

The project website has been set up for external communication purposes. It can be found at <https://www.arcticeberg.eu>. The project website will include information about the project, its objectives, results, partners and events.

5.3.2 General Requirements

You are requested to always indicate that the project has received funding from the European Union. Using the following:

- (a) display the EU emblem

The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text.

Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support.

When displayed in association with other logos (e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

- (b) include the following text (Disclaimer):

"Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."

- (c) include the project logo

You can find the logo and instructions on how to use it on the shared workspace [here](#).

5.4 Document Standard/Templates

All public documentation needs to conform to the document standards provided by the PC. The document standard could be used for:

- official EU reports (such as Periodic and Final);
- public documents by the consortium;
- project Deliverables (in a report format); and
- any documents that are declared as public by the consortium.

All project templates (Deliverables, presentations, etc.) will be created soon and saved on the shared project workspace.

5.4.1 Document Titles

To facilitate the identification of all documents produced during the project, a standard for document names shall be followed.

Table 7. Documentation guidelines

	Deliverables	Tasks	Meetings	Conferences
First letters	ICEBERG	ICEBERG	ICEBERG	ICEBERG
Underscore	–	–	–	–
Next letters	Deliverable number [Dx.y, where x=WP number and y=Deliverable number]	Task number [Tx.y, where x=WP number and y=Task number]	Type of document (i.e. Agenda, Minutes, Presentation). In case of presentation, include WP number.	Event title
Underscore	–	–	–	–
Next letters	Short explanatory title for the document.	Short explanatory title for the document.	Location and date of the meeting.	Location and date of the meeting.
Underscore	–	–	–	–
Next letters (for presentations only)			Short name of organisation and initials (for presentations)	Short name of organisation and initials of presenter
Underscore	–	–	–	–
Next letters	"v" and number of revision of this report [v0.1=draft version, v1.0=final version]	"v" and number of revision of this document [v0.1=draft version, v1.0=final version]	"v" and number of revision of this document [v0.1=draft version, v1.0=final version]	"v" and number of revision of this document [v0.1=draft version, v1.0=final version]

Deliverable documents:

[ICEBERG_Dx.y_Title_v1.0]

example: ICEBERG_D6.1_QAP_v1.0

Task documents:

[ICEBERG_Tx.y_Title_v1.0]

example: ICEBERG_T6.2_Quality assurance_v1.0

Meeting documents:

[ICEBERG_Type of Document_Location_DDMMYYYY_Organisation_v1.0]

example: ICEBERG_Agenda_Oulu_21022024_UOULU_v1.0

example: ICEBERG_Minutes_Zoom_23022024_UOULU_v1.0

Conference presentations:

[ICEBERG_Event_Location_DDMMYYYY_Organisation_Initials_v0.1]

example: ICEBERG_Event_Helsinki_25052024_UOULU_KR_v1.0

6 Reporting

Within the project, several reporting processes are in place to ensure both quality and timeliness of the Deliverables. There is an internal and an external reviewing process.

Throughout the lifetime of the project there are:

- Internal periodic report(s) (financial & technical progress);
- External Periodic report(s) to the EU (financial & technical progress).

Both are described in the following sections.

6.1 Reporting Calendar

To ensure timely submission, the partners should respect the following deadlines:

Table 8. Reporting Calendar

Kind of report	Period covered	Template ready and uploaded to ICEBERG workspace by PC	Deadline to send to PC	By whom?	Finalised & submitted to EC by the PC
Internal Periodic Report 1	M01-M09 (Jan. 2024-Sept. 2024)	M09 (Sept. 2024)	M10 (Oct. 2024)	Financial report by all consortium partners Technical report by WPLs	n/a
Internal Periodic Report 2	M10-M18 (Oct. 2024- June 2025)	M18 (June 2025)	M19 (July 2025)	Financial report by all consortium partners Technical report by WPLs	n/a
Periodic Report 1 to the EC	M01-M18 (Jan. 2024- June 2025)	M18 (June. 2025)	M19 (July 2025)	Financial report by all consortium partners Technical report by WPLs	M20 (Aug. 2025)
Internal Periodic Report 3	M19-M27 (July. 2025-Mar. 2026)	M27 (Mar. 2026)	M28 (Apr. 2026)	Financial report by all consortium partners Technical report by WPLs	n/a
Internal Periodic Report 4	M28-M36 (Apr. 2026-Dec. 2026)	M36 (Dec. 2026)	M37 Jan. 2027	Financial report by all consortium partners Technical report by WPLs	n/a
Periodic Report 2 to the EC	M19-M36 (July 2025-Dec. 2026)	M36 (Dec. 2026)	M37 (Jan. 2027)	Financial report by all consortium partners Technical report by WPLs	M38 (Feb. 2027)
Final Report	M1-M36 (Jan. 2024-Dec. 2026)	n/a	n/a	Project Coordinator	M38 (Feb. 2027)

6.2 Internal Periodic Reports

Internal periodic reports are compiled every nine months. An internal periodic report is an internal project document, meaning that it is not sent to the EU. The objective of this internal report is to monitor project expenditure and technical progress. It should be a summary of the technical work completed as well as a brief explanation for any deviations (budget and content!) from the DoA (EU GA, Annex 1).

An **internal periodic report** includes:

- **A description of the technical progress, per work package**
WPLs are responsible for gathering all information about the technical progress in their WP from their TLs and compile a WP report before sending it to the PC.
- **A financial overview from each partner**
The process of handing in the financial overview goes as follows:
 - 1) Reporting template excel sheet can be found on ICEBERG workspace a month before the deadline;
 - 2) This template should be filled out by **all the consortium partners**. The currency used must be EURO and the time worked must be calculated in person-months (PMs). A guide for how to calculate PMs can be found [here](#). This template provides the PC with valuable information needed for monitoring purposes and management reporting;
 - 3) The PC consolidates the provided information and sends the complete report to the consortium for review. Again, it will not be sent to the Commission. The reporting template is aligned with the partner budget and Periodic Reporting titles.

6.3 Periodic Report

Periodic Reports are done according to the EU GA. They include not only the technical contributions done within the reporting period (with special focus on innovation, progress beyond state of the art) but also contain detailed information by all partners about costs, efforts and the specific contribution per partner.

Just like the internal periodic report, the periodic report consists of a technical report and a financial report. As the interim payments are based on timely and proper submission of the periodic reports, all partners are required to contribute as necessary. Delay of the required reports will result in a delay of the interim payments!

The periodic report (EU GA: Article 21.2) must be submitted by the Project Coordinator **within 60 days** following the end of each reporting period. This report must include explanations for any deviations (budget and content) from the DoA (EU GA, Annex 1).

The 'periodic report' consists of two parts:

- Part A is generated by the IT system. It is based on the information entered by the participants through the periodic report and continuous reporting modules of the electronic exchange system in the Participant Portal. The participants can update the information in the continuous reporting module at any time during the life of the project. Part A contains:
 - the cover page;
 - a summary which can be used for publications by the EC;

- the answers to the questionnaire (covering issues related to the project implementation and the economic and social impact).

The Project Coordinator is responsible for part A.

- Part B is the narrative part that includes explanations of the work carried out by the beneficiaries during the reporting period. Part B needs to be uploaded as a PDF document following the template of Part B Periodic Technical report.

WPLs compile a report on their WP together with their TLs (Part B) and send it to the Project Manager one month before the deadline. The Project Manager consolidates the provided information and sends the complete periodic technical report to the consortium for review. The final approved version will be uploaded into the Participant Portal by the Project Manager.

The Periodic Report Template can be found on the EC website under HE reference documents: [periodic-report horizon-euratom_en.pdf \(europa.eu\)](#). An adapted word version of the Periodic Report Template will be shared with all consortium partners by the project coordinator before each reporting period.

The 'periodic financial report' consists of:

- Individual financial statement (EU GA: Annex 4) for each partner, for the reporting period concerned. This financial statement must detail the eligible costs for each budget category calculated in EURO and person-months (PMs). Each partner and linked third parties must declare all eligible costs, even if costs exceed the amounts indicated in the estimated budget;
- An explanation of the use of resources and information on subcontracting and in-kind contributions provided by third parties from each partner for the reporting period concerned.

A 'periodic summary financial statement' will be created automatically by the electronic exchange system, consolidating the individual financial statements of the partners, including the request for interim payment.

The Participant Contacts, Project Financial Signatories (PFSIGN) and Task Managers of each partner will be able to complete online their own Financial Statement including the explanations on the use of resources (also for their third parties). The Project Coordinator will have a final check on the statements and submit them electronically to the EC.

6.4 Final Report

In addition to the periodic report for the last reporting period, the PC must submit the final report within 60 calendar days following the end of the last reporting period.

The final report includes the following:

- 1) **'Final technical report'** with a summary for publication containing:
 - an overview of the results and their exploitation and dissemination;
 - the conclusions on the action;
 - the socio-economic impact of the action.

The PC compiles this final technical report in consultation with the partners.

2) **'Final financial report'** containing:

- a 'final summary financial statement' will be created automatically by the electronic exchange system, consolidating the individual financial statements of the partners for all reporting periods;
- a 'certificate on the financial statements' for each partner (and for each linked third party) if it requests a total contribution of EUR 430 000 (or more) reimbursement of actual costs and unit costs.

6.5 Financial Reporting in Detail

6.5.1 Budget

The budget contains the estimated eligible costs, broken down by Partner (and linked third party) and budget category (EU GA: Articles 5, 6).

The budget is based on estimated costs and person months. Frequent internal reporting ensures that these budgets are monitored well and that under- and overspending is noticed at an early stage. Please note that in reporting, actual costs must be reported and not budgeted ones. The budget can be viewed by the project partners on the Participant Portal and in the Grant Agreement, which is available on our shared workspace [here](#).

All amounts must be specified in EURO. Beneficiaries and linked third parties with accounting established in a currency other than the EURO must convert the costs recorded in their accounts into EURO. Use the average of the daily exchange rates published in the Official Journal of the European Union, calculated over the corresponding reporting period. If no daily EURO exchange rate is published, the costs must be converted to the average of the monthly accounting rates published on the Commission's website, calculated over the corresponding reporting period. Beneficiaries and linked third parties with accounting established in EURO must convert costs incurred in another currency into EURO according to their usual accounting practices.

The budget categories are listed in the EU GA: Article 6.2, these are:

- A. Direct personnel costs:
- costs for employees (or equivalent);
 - costs for natural persons working under a direct contract;
 - costs of personnel seconded by a third party against payment;
 - costs for SME owners without salary;
 - costs for beneficiaries that are natural persons without salary.
- B. Other direct costs:
- travel costs and related subsistence allowances;
 - equipment costs;
 - costs of other goods and services.
- C. Direct costs of subcontracting

If necessary to implement the action, the partner may award subcontracts covering the implementation of certain action tasks described in the GA. The partner must award the subcontracts ensuring the best value

for money or, if appropriate, the lowest price. In doing so, it must avoid any conflict of interests (EU GA: Article 35).

- D. Direct costs of providing financial support to third parties (if option applies)
- E. Costs of in-kind contributions not used on partner's premises (if option applies)
- F. Indirect costs:

Indirect costs should be calculated as: $0,25 \times (\text{direct personnel costs (A)} + \text{other direct costs (B)} - \text{Costs of in-kind contributions not used on the partner's premises } \text{€})$. Note that the costs of subcontracting are excluded from this 25% flat-rate.

- G. Specific cost categories (not applicable)

6.5.2 Individual Financial Statement – Declaration of Eligible Costs

The individual financial statement needs to be submitted electronically by each partner to the EU through the Participant Portal (EU GA: Annex 4).

The procedure below needs to be updated once this process is available in the EU Participant Portal of the Project:

- 1) Login to the Participant Portal.
- 2) Choose the tab 'my Projects'. If ICEBERG is not listed, contact the project manager of your organisation to add you as 'participant contact'.
- 3) Click 'Manage project'.
- 4) Click on the 'Financial statement'. Fill in the requested information with explanations.
- 5) Participant Contacts, Project Financial Signatories and Task Managers of each partner will be able to complete online their own Financial Statement including the explanations on the use of resources.
- 6) Once everything is filled in, click the "Lock for Review" button. Only Participant Contact can do this!
- 7) The Project Financial Signatory (PFSIGN) will be asked by email to sign the financial statement electronically.
- 8) Project Financial Signatory (PFSIGN) signs electronically the Financial Report and submits it to the PC to include it in the Periodic Report.
- 9) The PC will make a final check and then submit the financial statements including all reports to the EU through the Participant Portal.

6.5.3 Audit – Certificate on the Financial Statements

A Certificate on the Financial Statements (CFS) is requested for each partner in case of total contribution of EUR 430 000 or more, as reimbursement of actual costs and unit costs. This means excluding the reimbursement of indirect costs (25%).

Partners submit:

- either one certificate per reporting period. Note: choose this option, only when you expect to exceed the threshold of EUR 430 000 at the end of the project;
- or a single CFS for the whole project.

In both cases, the certificate and related costs may only be submitted with the final financial report.

Please note that you must keep the financial records of the expenses in this project for a minimum of 5 years after the final payment has been received – digital or hardcopy.

The template is available on the shared workspace [here](#).

6.6 Keeping records – supporting documentation

For a period of five years after the payment of the balance, each partner must keep records and other supporting documentation to prove the proper implementation of the action and the declared costs to be eligible. The documents need to be the original documents. Digital and digitalized documents are accepted if national law accepts these documents as originals.

The partners must keep the records and documentation according to their usual cost accounting practices and internal control procedures. There must be a track between the amounts declared, the amounts recorded in accounts and the amounts stated in the supporting documentation (audit trail).

For the different cost categories, consider the following documents:

Direct personnel costs:

- monthly signed time sheets (6.6.1 Time recording);
- calculation of daily rate (EU GA: Article 6.2);
- proof of paid salary;
- labour contracts.

Other direct costs (travel costs and related subsistence allowances, equipment costs, costs of other goods and services):

- quotations contracts;
- all receipts of expenditure;
- meeting docs: presence lists, minutes, agendas;
- calculations of depreciation costs charged to the project.

Direct costs of subcontracting:

- quotations subcontracts;
- signed subcontracting agreements.

6.6.1 Time recording

For personnel costs (declared as actual costs or on the basis of unit costs), the partners must keep time records for the number of hours declared. The time records must be in writing (hardcopy or digital) and approved by the people working on the action and their supervisors, at least monthly.

The time recording can be done by using a timesheet on paper or in a computer-based system. A template for timesheets is available in the shared workspace: [ICEBERG Template Time Declaration.docx \(sharepoint.com\)](#). This template is not mandatory; beneficiaries may use their own model, provided that it fulfils the minimum conditions and it contains at least the information detailed below.

Time records should include:

- the title and number of the project, as specified in the EU GA;
- the partners full name, as specified in the EU GA;

- the full name, date and signature of the person working for the project;
- the number of days worked for the action in the period covered by the time record;
- the supervisor's full name and signature;
- a reference to the work package described in the DoA (EU GA: Annex 1), to easily verify that the work carried out matches the work assigned and the person-months reported to the action;
- information included in timesheets must match records of annual and sick leave taken, and work-related travel.

6.6.2 Budget transfers

With the consent of the General Assembly, a re-distribution of person-months between partners may be considered. This re-distribution is allowed without requesting an amendment (EU GA: Article 5.5) provided that it does not imply a substantial change to the action as described in the EU GA. All other re-allocations of budget items need to be discussed in order to decide whether to apply for an amendment to the EU GA.

The maximum grant amount (EU GA: Article 5) can however NEVER be increased.

7 Payments

The following types of payments are foreseen:

1) **Pre-financing at the start of the project:**

Funding of costs will be paid to Parties without undue delay according to the pre-financing instalment schedule here below and provided the Project Coordinator has received the pre-financing payment from the Funding Authority.

Pre-financing funds remain EU property until they are 'cleared' against eligible costs accepted by the European Commission and until the payment of balance.

2) **Interim payment following the approval of the periodic reports:**

After approval of the formal periodic reports, an interim payment will be issued.

First Periodic Report: January 2024 (M1) – June 2025 (M18)

Second Periodic Report: July 2025 (M19) – December 2026 (M36)

3) **Final payment following the approval of the final report:**

The final payment will be transferred after the approval of the final report. It consists of payment according to the difference between the calculated total EU contribution (on the basis of the eligible costs) and the amounts already paid.

8 Deliverables

8.1 List of Deliverables and Milestones in chronological order

Table 9. List of Deliverables and Milestones

WP	No	Title	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Level	Due Date (month)	Delivery Date to EC
WP6	M1	Project Board and external Advisory Board meeting – kick off meeting	UOULU			M1	31 Jan 2024
WP5	M2	Creation of 1 to 3 social media channels for the project	KASKAS			M1	31 Jan 2024
WP5	M3	Successful establishment of internal DECO Board	KASKAS			M2	29 Feb 2024
WP5	D5.1	Website	KASKAS	DEC	PU	M3	31 Mar 2024
WP5	D5.2	DECO Strategy	KASKAS	DEC	PU	M3	31 Mar 2024
WP5	D5.6	First CDE Report	KASKAS	Report	PU	M3	31 Mar 2024
WP6	D6.1	Quality Assurance Plan	UOULU	Report	PU	M3	31 Mar 2024
WP4	M4	Internal project workshop to develop co-production methods, co-develop Code of Conduct for Diverse, Equitable, and Inclusive (DEI) research, co-develop citizen science framework, and contribute to ethics evaluation framework	WoA			M5	31 May 2024
WP4	D4.2	CoC for DEI	WoA	Report	PU	M6	30 Jun 2024
WP6	D6.2	First Data Management Plan	UFZ	DMP	PU	M6	30 Jun 2024
WP6	D6.3	Ethics Management Plan	UOULU	Other	PU	M6	30 Jun 2024
WP1	M5	Completion of first round of fieldwork (sample and data collection) → prerequisite for M13	forScience			M10	31 Oct 2024
WP1	M6	Specified ensembles of Lagrangian trajectories that coincide with major ship traffic routes, together with calibrated, representative reference solutions of the plankton ecosystem model (unperturbed, without ship disposals)	GEOMAR			M12	31 Dec 2024
WP1	D1.4	Status report	forScience	Report	PU	M15	31 Mar 2025
WP3	M7	Assessment and synthesis of multi-level governance completed	CAU			M15	31 Mar 2025
WP6	D6.4	Mid-term Data Management Plan	UOULU	DMP	PU	M18	30 Jun 2025

WP	No	Title	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Level	Due Date (month)	Delivery Date to EC
WP1	M8	Successful completion of incubation experiments with different types of pollutants	GEOMAR			M20	30 Aug 2025
WP4	M9	Stakeholder mapping: landscape, information exchange and co-development of new knowledge	WoA			M20	30 Aug 2025
WP1	M10	Completion of second round of fieldwork (sample and data collection) → prerequisite for M13	forScience			M22	31 Oct 2025
WP4	D4.1	Co-creation / citizen science framework and lessons learned	UFZ	Report	PU	M24	31 Dec 2025
WP2	M11	Community workshops & interviews for identification of observed and perceived changes, impacts, risks completed	UOULU			M24	31 Dec 2025
WP3	M12	First discussion on policy briefs content	ULAP			M24	31 Dec 2025
WP1	M13	Laboratory analyses of collected samples and data interpretation → prerequisite for D1.1, D1.2	GEOMAR			M26	28 Feb 2026
WP2	D2.1	Report on analysis of community observations of changes, impacts, risks and vulnerabilities and resulting strategies	UOULU	Report	PU	M28	30 Apr 2026
WP2	D2.6	CBEM Program	UOULU	Report	PU	M28	30 Apr 2026
WP1	D1.1	Table of top Antibiotic Resistance Genes of Concern for Human Health Pollutants table	GEOMAR	DATA	PU	M30	30 Jun 2026
WP1	D1.2	Report on pollution sources, distribution (standing stocks), and dynamics in the European Arctic	UOULU	Report	PU	M30	30 Jun 2026
WP2	D2.2	Table of emerging hazards	ONIRIS	DATA	PU	M30	30 Jun 2026
WP2	D2.3	Report on food chain contamination	ONIRIS	Report	PU	M30	30 Jun 2026
WP2	D2.4	Report on human health impacts of micro- and nano-plastics and other contaminants (PFAS)	INRAE	Report	PU	M30	30 Jun 2026
WP2	D2.5	Report on climate related observations and forecasts	BSC	DATA	PU	M30	30 Jun 2026
WP3	D3.1	Policy-recommendations report 1	ULAP	Report	PU	M30	30 Jun 2026
WP3	D3.3	Policy brief EU on prevention of plastic + chemical pollution	ULAP	Report	PU	M30	30 Jun 2026
WP3	D3.4	Policy brief on prevention of plastic + chemical pollution (AC+ science funders)	ULAP	Report	PU	M30	30 Jun 2026

WP	No	Title	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Level	Due Date (month)	Delivery Date to EC
WP4	D4.3	Gender White Paper	WoA	Report	PU	M30	30 Jun 2026
WP4	D4.4	Toolbox	WoA	Report	PU	M30	30 Jun 2026
WP3	D3.2	Policy-recommendations report 2	CAU	Report	PU	M32	31 Aug 2026
WP5	D5.4	Guidebook	KASKAS	DEC	PU	M33	30 Sep 2026
WP5	D5.5	Video	KASKAS	DEC	PU	M33	30 Sep 2026
WP1	D1.3	Report on impacts of pollution in the European Arctic	GEOMAR	Report	PU	M34	31 Oct 2026
WP5	D5.3	Final CDE Report	KASKAS	Report	PU	M36	31 Dec 2026
WP6	D6.5	Final Data Management Plan	UOULU	DMP	PU	M36	31 Dec 2026

8.2 Approval process of Deliverables

WPLs are responsible for their WP Deliverables. Members of the AB can be consulted by the WPLs or the PC during this whole process.

The quality review process should respect the following timeline:

- 1) The TL responsible for the Deliverable sends the final draft version v0.1 to the WPL;
- 2) WPL does the first check of the Deliverable and will send it **three weeks before the due date to the Project Management Group** for a review: iceberg-pmg@lists oulu.fi;
- 3) Members of the PMG have one week to give their feedback;
- 4) The WPL sends the final deliverable to **the PC one week before the due date for a final check and approval**;
- 5) ICEBERG PM uploads the Deliverable to the Participant Portal (final submission to the EC) and to the Internal Communication Platform. In case the Deliverable production occurs in a period with, e.g. public holidays the author should timely agree on an alternative feasible timeline with the readers and the PC.

9 Dissemination of results and open access

The partners must - as soon as possible (but not before a decision on their possible protection) — disseminate their results (i.e. make them public). Some of the classic forms of dissemination are:

- website or social media channels;
- peer-reviewed publication (open access);
- presentation at a scientific conference.

The dissemination measures should, however, be consistent with the 'DECO strategy' (D5.2) and proportionate to the impact expected from the action. D5.2 will provide more guidelines.

When deciding on dissemination, the partners must also consider the other partners' legitimate interests.

9.1 Open access to scientific publications

Each partner must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results.

In particular, it must:

- as soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications.

Moreover, the partner must aim to deposit at the same time, the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.

- ensure open access to the deposited publication — via the repository — at the latest:
 - on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or
 - within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case.
- ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identifies the deposited publication.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- the terms "European Union (EU)" and "Horizon Europe";
- the name of the action, acronym and grant number;
- the publication date and length of embargo period if applicable;
- a persistent identifier.

9.2 Dissemination rules

The complete rules for dissemination are covered in Section 8.4 of the CA and Article 17 of the EU GA.

More concrete, the partner wishing to publish, present or disclose information about the project must follow the following procedure:

Table 10. Prior notice time to the whole consortium by email

Type of dissemination / communication	Prior notice time before submitting the publication
Peer-reviewed scientific journal articles	3 weeks
Theses (Ph.D./M.Sc./B.Sc.)	3 weeks
Conference publications (abstracts and posters)	1 week
Articles in professional magazines (no peer review)	2 weeks
Press releases	2 weeks
General promotion in social media, company newsletters etc.	no prior notice

- An objection is justified if:
 - the objecting party's legitimate academic or commercial interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed;
 - the projection of the objecting party's results or background is adversely affected.
- The objection has to include a precise request for necessary modifications.
- The objecting partner can request a publication delay of not more than 45 calendar days from the time it raises such an objection. After 45 calendar days, the publication is permitted, provided that Confidential information has been removed from the publication as indicated by the objecting partner.

A partner shall not include in any dissemination activity another partner's results or background without obtaining written approval, unless they are already published.

The author informs the PC when the planned publication has been accepted for publishing (for monitoring proposes).

After a publication, the information on the publication, including bibliographic details, must be sent to the PC and the WP5 leader - KASKAS (Paavo Antikainen, paavo.antikainen@kaskas.fi) for dissemination purposes.

9.2.1 General requirements

Unless the EC requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must:

- 1) display the EU emblem (when displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence):

Funded by the
European Union

- 2) include the following text (Disclaimer):

"Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."